

Electricity access in Madagascar Insights from GEP-OnSSET modeling

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Abbreviations

ADER: Agence de Développement de l'Électrification Rurale

AFDB: African Development Bank

GADM: Global Aviation Data Management

GEP: Global Electrification Platform

IEP: Integrated Energy Planning

INSTAT: Institut National de la Statistique

JIRAMA: Jiro sy Rano Malagasy

M300: Mission 300

OnSSET: Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool

PV: Photovoltaic

QGIS: Quantum Geographic Information System

RGPH-3: Recensement Général de la Population et de l'Habitation

SEforALL: Sustainable Energy for All

SHS: Solar Home Systems

Keywords

Energy access, electrification planning, mission M300, GEP-OnSSET

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Executive Summary

This study presents an evaluation of electrification scenarios in Madagascar using the geospatial modeling tool OnSSET. In a context where only 36% of the population has access to electricity (74% in urban areas and just 15% in rural areas), reaching 80% electrification by 2030 requires targeted planning that considers financial, geographic, and technical constraints. Two scenarios were simulated: one prioritizing the largest settlements, and the other focusing on areas with the lowest investment cost per capita. Results indicate that Scenario 2 is more cost-effective (USD 4,450 million), while Scenario 1 (USD 5,200 million) aligns better with existing infrastructure and ongoing electrification efforts. Sensitivity analysis, however, shows that electricity demand projections significantly influence both the least-cost technology mix and the total investment required.

1. Introduction

Madagascar’s national objective is to achieve 80% electricity access by 2030 [1], a target that requires an annual electrification growth rate of 8.8%. The country's new energy policy envisions a technology mix dominated by hydropower, which is expected to contribute up to 75% of total generation [2]. This ambition, however, presents significant challenges in a country where the majority of the population lives in rural areas, often sparsely populated and with limited financial capacity. Identifying the most suitable and cost-effective electrification strategy under such conditions is complex and requires tools capable of integrating geographic, demographic, and economic realities.

This study supports the M300 project led by the AFDB and World Bank and aims to demonstrate how the OnSSET modeling tool can support Madagascar’s electrification planning by more accurately reflecting and prioritizing locally available renewable energy resources. It also seeks to identify the optimal allocation between grid extension, mini-grids, and solar home systems (SHS) needed to connect at least 3.5 million additional households by 2030 at the lowest possible cost and the investment required.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data collection

Before initiating the modeling work in OnSSET, a preliminary phase focuses on data collection. This includes gathering both geospatial and non-geospatial datasets, which are then imported into QGIS for validation and cross-checking. The data come from multiple sources: medium voltage (MV) and high voltage (HV) line data are obtained from JIRAMA and the IEP platform by SeforALL, while information on mini-grids is provided by ADER (Rural Electrification Development Agency). Additional geospatial layers are sourced from various open data platforms. Regarding the non-geospatial data, which serve as input assumptions for the simulations, demographic data primarily comes from the report of Madagascar's National Institute of Statistics (INSTAT) on the third General Population and Housing Census (RGPH-3). Technical specifications and various cost parameters are collected from national experts at JIRAMA and ADER involved in the electricity sector, as well as from publicly available cost references for Sub-Saharan African countries.

Here is a table summarizing the collection of spatial data:

#	Dataset	Data type	source
1	Administrative boundaries	Polygon	GADM
2	Medium-voltage lines (Existing)	Lines	JIRAMA/ https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/madagascar-iep-tool-metadata

#	Dataset	Data type	source
3	Medium-voltage lines (Planned)	Lines	JIRAMA
4	Distribution transformers (MV/LV)	Points	JIRAMA/ https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/madagascar-iep-tool-metadata
5	Substations	Points	JIRAMA
6	High-voltage lines (Existing)	Lines	JIRAMA/ https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/madagascar-iep-tool-metadata
7	High-voltage lines (Planned)	Lines	JIRAMA
8	Road network	Lines	https://download.geofabrik.de/africa.html
9	Settlement clusters	Polygons	PopClusters - Mendeley Data
10	Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI)	Raster	https://globalsolaratlas.info/map
11	Small-scale hydropower sites	Points	https://energydata.info/dataset/small-and-mini-hydropower-potential-in-sub-saharan-africa
12	Wind velocity (m/s)	Raster	Global Wind Atlas
13	Travel time (min)	Raster	https://data.malariaatlas.org/
14	Night-time lights	Raster	https://eogdata.mines.edu/products/vnl/
15	Existing mini-grid locations	Points	ADER
16	Custom demand layer (if the bottom-up approach is included)	Raster	https://energydata.info/dataset/madagascar-global-electrification-platform-gep**
17	Location of Health Facilities	Points	https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/madagascar-iep-tool-metadata
18	Location of Education Institutions	Points	https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/madagascar-iep-tool-metadata

2.2 Tool preparation

Once the GIS data has been cleaned and reprojected in QGIS using the WGS 84 coordinate system (EPSG:4326), the information contained in the collected GIS layers is processed and extracted using a Python script within a Jupyter Notebook. This step generates the input file required for integration into the modeling workflow. The next step is to calibrate the model to reflect the current situation of electrification.

2.3 Demand Analysis

- **Residential demand:** The value extracted from the "Customer Demand" GIS layer is calculated proportionally to the population:
Electricity demand target :
 - Urban target tier: 4 (1931 kWh/household/year)
 - Rural target tier large: 3 (395 kWh/household/year)
 - Rural target tier small: 1 (100 kWh/household/year)
- **Health facilities and education infrastructures:** The number of infrastructures per settlement multiplied by the average annual consumption value, based on reference values commonly used in rural electrification projects (ADER).
- **Commercial demand:** For each cluster, this value is estimated based on population intervals, taking into account income-generating activities commonly found in rural areas of Madagascar. The assumptions are informed by field experience from rural electrification projects

2.4 Supply options analysis

These are the key simulation assumptions used in the model:

- Planning Horizon: 2024–2030.
- Electrification target rate: 80%
- Demographics and social components:

Population by 2030	36 500 000
Urban ratio by 2030	40.9%
Urban household size	3.9
Rural household size	4.3
- Population Growth: 2.7% annual growth rate based on national estimate
- Minimum number of households in a settlement for mini-grids to be considered: 100
- rural_cutoff_size (Any rural settlement with fewer households is considered a "small rural " settlement: 50
- SA PV lifetime: 2 years (a value which reflects the typical quality of SHS currently sold in Madagascar)
- Commercial demand included
- Forced grid approach (Buffer distance (km) for automatic intensification): 15 km
- Maximum cost per household (USD/household): 120

2.5. Scenarios

Two realistic scenarios are considered for the country: forced national grid expansion and increased development of mini-grids, the latter primarily based on the number of rooftops per cluster.

- Scenario 1: The largest settlements first
- Scenario 2: Settlements based on the lowest investment cost per capita (low demand settlements first)

3. Results

This section of the report presents the results of our simulations, taking into account the various parameters described earlier.

- Scenario 1: *The largest settlements first*

The results obtained for this scenario are as follows:

Technology	Population 2030	New connections 2024-2030 (Households)	New Capacity 2024-2030 (MW)	Investment 2024-2030 (million USD)	Investment per connection (USD)
Grid densification	5 109 229	202 118	110.16	275.41	1 362.62
Grid extension	2 963 749	728 143	226.52	1 037.31	1 424.60
Solar Home System	9 956 222	2 552 689	403.33	1 513.78	593.01
Mini-grid_PV Hybrid	10 735 140	1 878 775	1 516.40	2 220.82	1 182.06
Mini-grid Wind	-	-	-	-	-
Mini-grid Hydro	435 834	108337	47.83	159.28	1 470.23
Non-electrified	7 300 228	-	-	-	-
Total	36 500 402	5 470 062	2 304.24	5 206.60	

In 2030, the objective of reaching an 80% electricity access rate is confirmed by the results of this Scenario. 29,200,174 people will have access to electricity through the following five technologies: grid extension and grid densification, stand-alone PV, hybrid PV mini-grids, and hydro mini-grids.

In terms of the number of beneficiaries, hybrid PV mini-grids and SA PV are the most dominant, accounting for 36.76% and 34.09% respectively. Similarly, the investments required for these two technologies are the highest: USD 2,220.82 million for hybrid PV mini-grids and USD 1,513.78 million for SA PV.

Among the five technologies, hydro mini-grids and grid extension show the highest level of investment per connection, respectively 1,470.23 USD and 1,424.60 USD.

The map below shows how the five technologies are distributed after Scenario 1.

- **Scenario 2: Settlements based on the lowest investment cost per capita (low demand settlements first)**

The results for this scenario are as follows:

Technology	Population 2030	New connection 2024-2030 (Households)	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)	Investment per connection (USD)
Grid densification	5 109 229	202 118	110.16	275.41	1 362.62
Grid extension	2 641 102	649 681	198.42	901.56	1 387.70
Solar Home System	13 438 528	3 445 982	435.08	1 833.82	532.16
Mini-grid_PV Hybrid	7 818 435	1 184 302	962.21	1 368.21	1 155.29
Mini-grid Wind	-	0	0	0	
Mini-grid Hydro	191 575	47 541	21.52	72.88	1 532.99
Non-electrified	7 300 073	0	0	0	0
Total	36 498 942	5 529 624	1 727,39	4 451.88	

In this scenario, 29,198,869 people will have access to electricity by 2030, representing 80% of the total population. As in Scenario 1, five technologies are considered: grid extension, grid densification, SA PV, hybrid PV mini-grids, and hydro mini-grids.

In terms of population covered, number of new connections, and investment cost, SA PV is by far the most significant as shown on the map below. The total installed capacity in 2030 is 1,727MW, more than half (55.7%) of which comes from hybrid PV mini-grids, and 25.2% from SA PV. As in the first scenario, the hydro mini-grids has the highest investment per connection with 1,532.99 USD.

- ***Differences between scenarios***

The following series of graphs illustrates the differences between the two electrification scenarios in 2030, in terms of population covered, number of new connections, installed capacity (MW), and investment cost (million USD).

Number of new connections by 2030

Investment cost by technology and by scenario

Installed capacity by technology and by scenario

The key differences between the two scenarios focus on two main points:

- The installed capacity of mini-grids is 1,516 MW in Scenario 1, compared to 962 MW in Scenario 2;
- In Scenario 1, the investment cost for SA PV is higher than that of hybrid PV mini-grids, whereas the opposite is observed in Scenario 2.

4. Discussion

The results above provide valuable insights for selecting a national electrification planning model for Madagascar. Specifically, the option "Settlements based on the lowest investment cost per capita (low demand settlements first)" maximizes the cost-to-coverage ratio — meaning a lower installed capacity per capita — while the "The largest settlements first" option is more aligned with the current technical, institutional, and financial realities of the country.

In our approach, we defined the Malagasy Government's objective of achieving an 80% electricity access rate by 2030 as the reference scenario. To reach this target, three technologies are prioritized, in the following order of importance: grid extension, stand-alone solar PV, and hybrid solar PV mini-grids. Both of our modelled scenarios produced results that are consistent with the reference scenario, but with a larger target population, as illustrated in the following figure.

In the reference scenario, it was estimated that 3.5 million people would have access to electricity by 2030, whereas Scenario 1 projects 5.47 million people and Scenario 2 projects 5.53 million. This difference can be attributed to the use of different demographic data sets in our simulations.

Scenarios	Population (2030)	Urban household size	Rural household size
Reference	35.5 million	5.5	5.5
Scenarios 1 and 2	36.5 million	3.9	4.4

The results of both scenarios revealed a very low share of hydro mini-grids. Given Madagascar’s significant hydropower potential, this technology should be more prominent in the simulation outcomes. As stated in the objective section of this report, Madagascar aims to achieve a renewable-dominant energy mix by 2030, with hydropower accounting for approximately 75%. Therefore, further analysis could focus on scenarios that highlight hydro-solar mini-grid combinations, which would help optimize the use of locally available natural resources.

Additionally, it was observed that the model does not account for the evolution of individual customer demand. Incorporating this parameter could have improved the realism of the demand projections.

Building on these results to develop regional-level electrification master plans would provide more localized insights and contribute to a more realistic national energy strategy. However, it is essential to improve the quality of geospatial datasets to ensure better accuracy. Additionally, incorporating productive uses of electricity into the modeling would add depth and reflect real-world usage patterns.

5. Conclusion

The analysis conducted in this report demonstrates that a least-cost electrification strategy enabling Madagascar to achieve an 80% electricity access rate by 2030 is feasible. To accomplish this, technological options must be prioritized according to territorial specificities. Based on the two scenarios studied, three strategic priorities have been identified:

- Extension and densification of the electricity grid within a 15 km buffer of existing infrastructure;
- Deployment of hybrid solar and hydro mini-grids in medium-sized rural settlements;
- Installation of stand-alone solar PV systems in remote and sparsely populated areas.

Finally, further work is required to refine the modeling outcomes. This should include the integration of region-specific socio-economic data, consideration of productive electricity uses, and identification of dominant renewable energy resources in each region. Additionally, enhancing the quality of geospatial datasets (GIS) will be essential to improve the reliability and precision of the results.

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